

NIGERIA’S FEDERALISM: A NEED FOR ANTHROPOLOGICAL RE-AMALGAMATION

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Abstract

Nigeria as a nation, is characterised by multi-ethnicity, multi-custom, multi-language, multi-religion, multi-traditional setting, and multi-political party today. Structured within these diversities by the colonial masters and amalgamated without proper ethnographic analysis of the multi-various diversities of the people for proper political, economic and administrative structure in-line with cultural diversities of the people. Hence, true federalism has remained an illusion. Against this backdrop, this theoretical paper examines the roles of anthropological data to engender a deep understanding of these diversities in order to harness them towards attaining true federalism in Nigeria. Federalism as a theory of regional integration was adopted by the researchers for theoretical explanations. Anthropological analysis discovered tribal attachment and primordial sentiments, religious fanaticism, and majority-minority debacle as great tools of national divide. Engagement of anthropological data from the cultural diversities and consideration of such towards a re-amalgamation as a form of melting-pot culture for a true national identity of the Nigerian state is recommended for solving Nigeria’s political and economic challenges.

Key words: Re-amalgamation, federalism, national divide and anthropological data

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is a nation state created by the British colonialists through the 1914 amalgamation of over 250 independent ethno-cultural nations. The amalgamation processes which were executed by Anthropologists ended up as a failure to engage anthropological data through proper ethnographic analysis of the multi-various cultural nations drafted into the processes. According to Mado (2016), the west used anthropologists as colonial masters in their colonization expeditions of Nigeria and other nations especially in Africa. The formation of the geo-territory called “Nigeria”, which comprised of many ethnic human groupings in the north and many ethnic human groupings in the south, resulted in an anthropological blunder, which created a panorama for ethnic and cultural domination of few cultural groupings over the many others and thence, the scramble for ethnic domination, ethnic relevance, ethnic control, majority –minority ethnic groups relations and ethnic

conflicts. Ethnocentrism became institutionalized in the day to day economic and political affairs, and other social relations of Nigerians. This has greatly influenced the quasi nature of federalism observed, identified, and experienced by Nigerians under various administrations of governments since her independent in 1960.

Tangban (2014) posited that not only did the colonial authorities bring together those disparate groups and systems to create Nigeria in a manner that disregarded the existing disparities in cultural values and preferences, but also failed to make nation-building part of the foundation of the forceful process of state-building. It was during that period that the nation was observed to have comprised many cultural groups which were in the colonial processes and later metamorphosed into the specie in the genus of multi-ethnic political and social communities in federalism (Tella, Doho and Bapeto, 2014). Nigeria was a large country comprising more than 250 ethnic groups combined differently to constitute the major pre-colonial political system and according to Nigerian historians and some political scientists, at that time were the stateless societies in the East, the Hausa state in the North and the centralized power Alafin in the former Oyo Empire in the West (Tella, Doho & Bapeto, 2014).

Ignoring the cultural differences that existed within the various ethnic nationalities before the amalgamation was not just an anthropological blunder, but a political blunder by the British who sought not the interest of the people, but how to achieve their exploitative economic agenda. According to Baba and Aeysinghe (2017), by amalgamating the various units without their consents under a single nation and central government, a political blunder has already been committed. The Nigerian state is struggling since then to recover from this blunder that incorporated the destinies of the unborn Nigerians who are born day after day into this anthropological and political error with generational influence. The resultant effect of that professional gaffe erupted in the Nigerian civil war of 1967, where the Nigerian government paraded the northern interest of national unity against the Biafran army of South-eastern interest, and in the conquest, the north has since built on supremacy in all aspects of the socio-economic and socio-political affairs of Nigeria. The situation still points to the erroneous methodology of the amalgamation processes adopted by the British even as professional anthropologists.

The issue behind the Nigeria's federation challenges is that, the problem of true federalism in Nigeria is rooted in the wrong methodology used by colonial anthropologists, instead of proper ethnographic analysis of the cultural characteristics of the multi-ethnic nationalities for proper national integration in a professional anthropological amalgamation processes. This paves the way to solutions which are in the adoption of the methodologies of the science that engages anthropological data in holistic studies of the origins and social relationship of humans in their cultural characteristics for a professional restructuring and re-integration which will lead to real re-amalgamation of these multi-ethnic human groupings in Nigeria.

Ethnic structure and inequality in Nigeria
 In Osimen, Akinyemi and Samuel, (2013)

CONCEPTUAL AND THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVES

Federalism

Federalism theory as a theory of regional integration was abandoned too early because; it was linked to the development of the European Community, which was in crisis from the mid-1970s till the mid-1980s. Federalism theory of regional integration was propagated by the Riker-McKayian version; it provides a theory of how countries may unite peacefully. This approach must be developed in terms of (a) the concept of threat, which must be broadened to include economic, social, and cultural elements, and (b) the role of a basic common culture, which primarily facilitates the founding of the federation and constitutes the foundation securing the maintenance of the new federation (Oxford Research Encyclopaedias, 2018). Considering the two terms of the subject matter of the theory of federalism as a theory of regional integration, the first is concerned with treaty while the second is concerned with common culture. This explains that federalism is driven by treaty of the regions concerned and a creation of common culture to drive the federal identity.

According to Babalola (2013), the most notable work on the political theory of origin of federations is that of Riker, who made no pretense about his attempt to build a theory particularly on the origin of federations, and the operation and significance of federalism. Riker defined federalism as a bargain between prospective national leaders and officials of constituent governments for the purpose of aggregating territory, the better ways to lay taxes and raise armies (Babalola, 2013). The key phenomenon in federalism process is “bargain”, as extracted from Riker’s definition of federalism. In the amalgamation of the multi-ethnic nations to form a nation-state called Nigeria under a federated government or as a federated unit, “ethnic-bargain” was not adopted as a tool for the forceful welding of the multi-cultural human groupings. The bargain according to Riker is to be done by the constituents’ representatives and prospective national leaders. This explains what went wrong with the adopted methods which denied the real citizens of the newly created nation the opportunity to sit on bargaining tables for proper national integrated resolutions from their socio-cultural perspectives. Instead, it was a forceful fusing of people within separated cultural origins, and traditional settings (Peters and Bassey, 2019).

According to Federick (2008) in Tella, Doho and Bapeto (2014), federalism should be seen as a process by which unity and diversity are politically organized and these processes include political phenomena, persons, ideas and institutions put differently. Federalism from Federick (2008) position signifies a political harmonization of human groupings, ideologies and institutions. Harnessing these elements of a federal unit or nation is within the socio-political capacity of the various ethnic-nationalities to sit together on a pre-national table for bargains and compromise for a sustainable socio-cultural integration and national unity. Restructuring of the Nigeria’s socio-economic and socio-political arrangement is seeking an attempt to break the dividing walls of many ethnic differences for the creation of a federated nation.

Orluwene (2018) posits Nigerian federalism as a product of British economy which emerged on placement under different conditions. He noted that even the British did not know and realize its character and nature until after acquisition, hence it was involuntary and traumatic for some and for others it was at best, affection for the unknown. But for all of them, it was a forced brotherhood and sisterhood which has been the subject of continual tinkering, panel beating and even attempted dissolution (Ayoade, 1998 cited in Orluwene, 2018). Orluwene (2018) observed that no wonder another distinguished Nigerian political actor Obafemi Awolowo (1947) described Nigerian federalism as mere geographical expression, therefore an artificial creation. While another equally famous actor in Nigerian politics Ahmadu Bello (1962) described the making of Nigerian federation as the “mistake of 1914”.

Federalism, according to Tella, Doho and Bapeto (2014) is constitutionally created based on comprise of the various constituents. The implication of this is that, federalism does not provide for imposition of a federal constitution without the bargains of the various ethnic groupings and constituencies for a lasting compromise that shall convey the socio-cultural interest of the multi-ethnic nations. In other words, federalism is based on the power of the governing constitution formulated on the table of agreement of the various cultural parties which are drafted into national formation. Anthropologically, this supports a professional unionism of multi-ethnic human groupings through inter-cultural balance of agreed ideologies in nation creation.

National divides

The history of national divides is in the history of amalgamation of the multi-ethnic nationalities in 1914 by the British without proper ethnographical integration of the socio-

cultural differences. The 1914 amalgamation exercise embarked upon by Lord Lugard of the areas of North and South of the river Niger and Benue was unification without unity or at best unity in diversity entrenched in the absence of a national ideologically oriented political structure representing defined interests of Nigerians across the ethnic divide (Osimen, Balogun, and Adenegan, 2013). This is an indication of the absence of “bargains and compromise” which are the key elements of federalism as defined by Riker in Babalola (2013), and Tella, Doho and Bapeto (2014).

According to Tangban (2014), Nigeria is a deeply diversified state, being made up of about 250 ethnic groups. Apart from diversity in ethnicity, the country is also divided along religious lines. The northern part is principally a Muslim area, while the southern segment is predominantly a Christian area. However, in both segments, there are pockets of adherents of traditional religion (Tangban, 2014), which create neglect of certain people and areas (Usoro and Peters, 2019)

The division laid in the amalgamation gave rise to ethnic based political movements to fill the void in order to challenge the present distribution of power and wealth, demanding a restructuring of political system in such a way that will grant them equitable access to these properties (Osimen, Balogun, and Adenegan, 2013). Examples of such movements are Afenifere and the Odudua People's Congress, which represent the Yoruba ethnic group, while the Igbo is represented by Ohanaze Ndigbo. The Arewa consultative forum has emerged as the defender of northern interests who feels threatened by the challenges to their power and identity, while the South-South People's Assembly speaks for the Niger delta states, where contending ethnic organisations are vying for their particular ethnic interest which is not always in confluence with the universal interests (Osimen, Balogun and Adenegan, 2013).

Mackintosh in 1962 noted that Nigerian federation has always has peculiar features, the most evident being that it was not created by the coming together of separate states but was the subdivision of a country which had in theory been ruled as a single unit. He also observed that, the division into three regions left one, the Northern Region larger than the other two regions put together. This was a black politicking of manipulation for selfish interest (Peters, Usoro, and Basse, 2020). The black politic here was to set up a combined Northern Region of many ethnic nationalists to dominate the Southern and Eastern Regions forever. According to Mackintosh, this singular act of division led to the allocation of 174 seats in the Federal House of Representatives to represent a northern population of 17,573,000. The West, with 6,408,000 people was allocated 62 seats, and the east with 7,497,000 was allocated 73 seats, and Federal Territory of Lagos was allocated 3 seats. He noted that, the North alone could outvote all other region if they come out as a single block. Though there were other ethnic nationalities in the northern region, the act brought about the grouping of all ethnic nationalities as a single region against an ethnic divided South which was divided into West and East. Though there are other ethnic divisions springing up across the nation today, the foundation of division which was laid as explained by Mackintosh, still direct the present structure of Nigeria, and has greatly influenced Nigeria's federalism.

According to Orluwene (2018) the saying of the colonial governor of Nigeria, Hugh Clifford in Okpaga (2009) observed that: Nigeria is a collection of self-contained and mutually independent native states, separated from one another, as many of them are, by great distance, by differences of history and tradition, and by ethnological, racial, tribal, political, social and regional, barriers. Tangban (2014) observed that ethnic militias such as Odudua People Congress (OPC), the Movement for the Actualisation of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB), and the Arewa People Congress (APC), etc. are novel phenomenon and a creation of the political class in pursuit of their selfish political and economic interests, parading themselves as the military arms of the various ethnic groups in Nigeria. As a result,

their activities have escalated inter-group tensions with negative impact on national unity (Tangban, 2014).

Nigeria is a nation-state; made up of many cultural divides which create the existing case of ethnocentrism that influences the socio-economic, socio-political and socio-cultural relations among Nigerians. The divisions have in so many ways affected the practice of federalism by not creating the enabling working environment for it to thrive. The formulation of the Nigerian federated constitution is an indication that the federated nation call Nigeria is an imposition as the constitution we have today. The imposition is an adopted option from the colonialists over proper integration, which continually project national divides. Since proper ethno-cultural integration was not done or take into consideration by the British anthropologists, the amalgamation became a building on a faulty foundation. The fact that Nigeria as a nation was forcefully imposed on these multi-cultural ethnic human groupings, the division was only formalized at the end of the process, therefore, the call for re-amalgamation to properly integrate the different ethno-cultural groups for national unity.

Anthropological data

According to Lawuyi and Ololajulo (2011), anthropology, undoubtedly, is not a popular discipline in Africa and the reason for this could be the role it supposedly played in entrenching western rule and domination in the continent. They noted that if anthropology has retained its relevance in western societies, since it has persisted as a field of study, then, there certainly is in it, usefulness beyond being a tool of gaining understanding of native societies. We are, therefore, of the view that if, indeed, anthropological knowledge once aided the subjugation of Africa same knowledge holds the key for liberation and development (Lawuji and Ololajulo, 201). Anthropologists were the British instruments in the colonisation processes and the formation of Nigeria. The federation was an anthropological idea which was carried out without employing the anthropological data gathered by these anthropologists through ethnography. History has it that, the British colonial anthropologists were vast with the knowledge of the multi-ethnic nationalities discovered within the geographical landmark which they picked for a Nigerian nation. Though Orluwene (2018) posits that the British did not know and realize the heterogeneous cultural milieu of Nigeria until after acquisition, the position of Modo (2016), and Lawunyi and Ololajulo (2011) show that as anthropologists, the British as a matter of professionalism is concerned were vast with the knowledge of the cultural heterogeneity of Nigeria, but their methodology in the amalgamation of the various ethnic nationalities ignored the anthropological methodology.

Anthropological data are based on holistic view of the society and culture, that is, society is viewed as a whole system that is connected by strands of cultural traits, which though tend to be independent are interwoven for the overall sustenance of that culture (Asakitikpi, 2011). According to Asakitikpi (2011), anthropology tries to understand and comprehend why humans differ from each other both physically and culturally. He further stated that, due to the wide interest, the discipline cannot be precisely defined to capture its full interest. Holism in anthropology is develop on the premise that man as a complex being cannot be properly understood from one set of data. Holism is what makes anthropological data more unique, especially in amalgamation, integration and unification of cultural heterogeneous society. It takes holistic understanding of the cultural characteristic of man to appreciate his relations in his bids.

Many Nigerians today in reality know nothing about other Nigerians from other ethnic nationalities. This is the reason why we see ourselves as threat to one another and consider ourselves as enemies. Instead of coming together to forge ahead, we spend time and

resources fighting ourselves. The major factor behind these wars lies in the misplacement of anthropological data in nation building. Anthropologists use ethnography as major technique in field study of human groupings and human phenomena. Ethnography gives voice to people in their own local context (Fetterman, 2010). Ethnography enables proper understanding of the people through immersion into their culture (Peters, 2019). It is through this measure that each ethnic national will be able to appreciate the privilege of being part of what is considered as British mistake, while forging for a better federal nation.

Re-amalgamation

Re-amalgamation arises as a concept that seeks to readdress the amalgamation processes of heterogeneous locale as that of Nigeria as perpetuated by the British colonialists in Africa. Baba and Aeysinghe (2017) posit that the urgent task before Nigerians is how to reposition the union towards ameliorating those threats which affects their unity so as to sustain the age long national unity established since 1914. Re-amalgamation according to the context of this paper assesses the methodology employed and the expected aims of the anthropological blunder in the unification of multi-cultural ethnicities in the colonial era. Re-amalgamation is an anthropological movement to correct the unification of multi-cultural society created by anthropologists without engaging ethnographic analysis of cultural diversity as a professional anthropological technique. As a reaction to the amalgamation of the northern and southern proletariats of the river Niger, Benue and the delta creeks, it is a scientific quest to employ anthropological methods in proper ethnographic analysis of the socio-cultural differences that exist across Nigeria in order to achieve national integration for tolerance, unity, national identity, common national interest, and federalism. Re-amalgamation can also be elucidated as an attempt to create a “melting pot” culture toward nation building and federalism from a forceful unification of heterogeneous human groupings by the colonial masters.

Nigeria at the amalgamation of 1914 was not just a blunder or a mistake as stated by Baba and Aeysinghe (2017), but it was an anti-national time bomb with unpredictable date of explosion set up by the British colonial masters. The present ethnic agitations and crises of Biafra from the east, the Niger Delta militants from the south-south, the Boko Harams from the north, and Fulani herdsmen crises are pointing to the closeness to the date of the explosion if re-amalgamation is not considered, to unify the diversity of ethnic interest, and restructure Nigeria for a working federal state. According to Osimen, Balogun, and Adenegan (2013), if there is any time to address the ethnic question in Nigeria again, it has to be now. Dickson (2013) as quoted by Osimen, Balogun, and Adenegan (2013), stated that a nation held hostage to preventable events of tragic nature and at the front burner repeatedly are known issues we have refused to face squarely: Who we are? where we belong, what we represents, what does Nigeria mean to us? do we want to remain one? and how?

The process of re-amalgamation is the engagement of anthropological analysis of the many differences which exist in the lines of inter-relation, inter-dependent, and co-existence of the various ethnic groups within the geographical sphere of Nigeria. This will lead to “bargains” and “compromise” as stated in Riker’s federalism in Bablola (2013) and Tella, Doho, and Bapeto, (2014), on the table of national restructuring, to accommodate opinions, interests, demands, and political ideologies of the various ethnicities, against continuous forceful unification which may only be for continual internal conflicts that weaken national unity and national strength and integration.

NEXUS BETWEEN ANTHROPOLOGICAL DATA, RE-AMALGAMATION AND FEDERALISM IN NIGERIA

Anthropology in its data gathering techniques provides for intimate human encounter (Akinsete, 2011). The provision to engage with human culture in a holistic dimension makes anthropology to focus on humans, humans' problems and humans' future. The holistic study of human culture through ethnography brings to bare appropriate understanding of the cultural dimensions of an ethnic group. In amalgamation of a multi-cultural nation like Nigeria, proper understanding of the cultural differences by the different ethnic nations would have formed the basis, from which the bargains and later compromise for the creation of a federal nation follows. The anthropologists, who embarked on the 1914 amalgamation of the people of Nigeria, failed in their anthropological mandate.

Ethnographic analysis of the cultural differences that exist within the Nigerian society will open the eyes of understanding of Nigerians to our origins and ethno-cultural differences. This will compel Nigerians to appreciate the diversity that exists in our nationality or nationhood, for the projection of a national culture. Ethnography as anthropological methodology of data collection helps in presenting an emic analysis of a given cultural human groupings, by presenting their strength, economic potentials, political ideologies, pattern variables of natural environmental adaptability, against the etic analysis which always gives rise to ethnocentrism that generate conflicts.

Socio-cultural analysis of the many ethnic nations within the boundaries of Nigeria can enhance re-amalgamation through the formation of a melting pot culture. The melting pot culture as in the United States of America has the anthropological capacity to harness all other ethno-culture to a united Nigerian culture. The subject of Nigerian culture is the place of socio-cultural integration of the ethnic differences through the use of anthropological data for a social and cultural re-amalgamation of the heterogeneous country. The development of a Nigerian culture is an anthropological challenge facing Nigerians in the face of ethnic divisions, agitations and crises. A working federalism in a multi-ethnic nation like Nigeria can only be possible in a melting pot culture.

Melting pot culture provides for national identity through national dialogue, bargains, compromise, and agreement on a Nigerian image, which by agreement of the various representatives of the ethnic nationalities, is given power to swallow every other cultural identity at national level. This anthropological experiment is already at work in the United States of America. The Nigerian society can begin to produce, Hausa-Nigerians, Igbo-Nigerians, Gbaya-Nigerians, Kanuri-Nigerians, Yoruba-Nigerians, Ibibio-Nigerians, Annang-Nigerians, Tiv-Nigerians and so on.

Our strength as a nation lies in our unity and national cohesion (Baba and Aeysinghe, 2017). One of the greatest countries in the world is the United States of America, and it is also one of the most diverse in ethnicity, race and religion. Its greatness is rooted in its diversity which is being utilized to advantage and actively promoted by the American people (Obasanjo, 2016 and Olatunji, 2016 cited in Baba and Aeysinghe, 2017).

Re-amalgamation anthropologically, advocates for proper ethnographic analysis of the various ethnic groupings for a cultural integration by restructuring via bargains and agreements for a creation of a national identity or image (melting pot culture). To correct the colonialists' blunder of ignoring the ethnic diversity that exists in Nigeria by the colonial British, it is appropriate to readdress the cultural diversity for cultural integration which is the basis for true federalism.

CONCLUSION

Nigeria is a cultural heterogeneous nation in creation. The 1914 blunder as noted by Baba and Aeysinghe (2017), called amalgamation by the British anthropologists as noted by Modo (2016) and Lawuyi and Ololajulo (2011), has given the nation more issues of crises than issues of celebrations. The ratio between conflicts and celebration is directly proportional to the ethnic divides which drive the entire day to day activities within the nation. Ranging from politics, resources allocation and control, appointments and employment, distributions of national parastatals and institutions, to award of national honours, the divides remain visible. The pretence we as Nigerians show in inter-ethnic relations does not holds back the Niger Delta militants, the Biafra movement, the Boko Harams and the recent Fulani herdsmen killing. These scenarios contribute to the quasi federalism operated in Nigeria. According to Osimen, Balogun and Adenegan, (2013), if there is any time to address the ethnic question in Nigeria again, it has to be now. Re-amalgamation advocates restructuring of the nation through employment of ethnographic analysis of the ethno-cultural interests of every ethnic group toward building a national culture. By national culture we mean the re-amalgamation of all ethnic nations in a melting-pot culture. Borrowing from the United States of America, where the national culture projects “America First” among every ethno-national American, the re-amalgamation project of Nigeria in this perspective advocates a national culture for a national identity. It is expedient to conclude this work with the words of Lawuyi and Ololajulo (2011), who posit that if indeed anthropological knowledge once aided in the subjugation of Africa, same knowledge holds the key for liberation and development.

RECOMMENDATION

Re-amalgamation through restructuring, cultural integration, bargains and compromise at this time is a necessary venture to harmonize the socio-cultural differences that exist between Nigerians. The professional methods for this all time needed assignment should include Riker’s ideology of true federalism; “bargains”, the Tella, Doho and Bapeto (2014) ideology of federalism; “compromise”, the Ray’s ideology of true federalism; “division of power and states’ sovereignty”, and anthropological dimension which are proper consideration and harmonization of the socio-cultural differences for a national culture. This national culture will then promote national interest and national identity over ethical interest and tribal identity among Nigerians. Being able to reach this socio-cultural height in our national socio-political dealings is the attainment of true federalism in Nigeria.

It will be good for national unity and true federalism to see a Nigerian president and other key national office holders, wear the cultural attires of the various ethnic groups in Nigeria for their official duties as the occasion may demand instead of day to day appearance in their own cultural attires only.

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